

Towards Decoding Schema: Unveiling Patterns of Subtle Discrimination Through Data-Driven Analysis

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Abstract

Psychologists have long used schema questionnaires to measure maladaptive schemas, which are beliefs and emotions that shape how individuals interpret and engage with the world. By identifying an individual's dominant schemas, interventions can be developed to improve their daily functioning and well-being. This study explores the Helsinki region's dominant schemas of international labor forces on their demographic characteristics and attributes. We analyze common schemas and investigate potential factors that influence the prevalence of these schemas among individuals and groups.

Methods: A survey with tailored schema-based questions was developed and distributed to the intended population (N = 91). We conducted semi-structured interviews with individuals who had encountered covert discrimination in their workplaces. Participants were classified based on similarity in answers to questionnaires and schema profiles using advanced statistical methods and machine-learning models, identifying important maladaptive schemas and studying their correlation with demographic factors.

Results: Our data analysis indicates that participants' demographic characteristics have minimal influence on their dominant schemas. Mistrust and entitlement emerge as the most significant schemas among participants. The primary contributors to variance are mistrust, abandonment, emotional deprivation, and social isolation, suggesting a higher vulnerability to discrimination due to heightened sensitivity to trust-related issues. A smaller portion of variance is attributed to entitlement and failure schemas, indicating a tendency towards displaying discriminatory behavior based on a strong sense of entitlement and self-importance.

The implication of our study: Our novel approach identifies distinct schema profiles within the participant population, offering new research opportunities for academics and enabling targeted interventions to address the specific attitudes and behaviors of individuals or groups, fostering a more inclusive and diverse society.

Keywords: Data mining, schemas questionnaire, subtle discrimination

Introduction

For several decades, psychologists have utilized schema questionnaires as means of assessing maladaptive schemas. These schemas play a crucial role in shaping individuals' beliefs and emotions and influencing their interactions with the world. The questionnaire is specifically designed to identify dominant schemas that originated during early developmental stages and have contributed to various emotional and behavioral patterns. By determining an individual's schema profile, therapists can develop targeted interventions aimed at enhancing their daily functioning and overall well-being. These interventions address the maladaptive schemas and their associated challenges, promoting healthier ways of thinking and behaving. In this study, our objective was to explore the relationship between schemas and the likelihood of experiencing discrimination in group analysis. We aimed to uncover a connection between schemas and both the occurrence and impact of discriminatory experiences.

In his 2005 book "Status Anxiety" (De Botton, 2005) argues that job assignments before 1750 were based on the individual's identity. This approach was deemed acceptable by society at the time. However, after 1750, this trend began to change. Personnel were hired solely based on their skills and abilities. Therefore, connection-based hiring is replaced by competence-based recruiting. This was a crucial factor in rapid industrial development. Europe and the United States, in particular, have invested significantly in recruiting professionals from other countries. Although competency-based recruiting produces positive results, it has some drawbacks, such as individual anxiety about career advancement and a competitive attitude toward developing competencies among candidates and coworkers. Anxiety and competitiveness such as wage, positions, and status (Stuart, 2006) are often the source of "subtle" discrimination in the contemporary working environment. The definition of subtle discrimination is ambiguous and unclear. Since it is difficult to detect subtle discrimination, it often remains unnoticed. Work environments display a wide range of attitudes toward individuals or groups. In addition to job status, manager attitude, personality, and workplace culture, employees' cultural backgrounds may also play a role. A key objective of this study is to investigate the schemas that impact the foreign workforce and identify the relationship between them and subtle discrimination. Subtle discrimination often occurs without leaving any trace (Rowe, 1990) for the oppressor, who is engaged with the victims either directly or indirectly. Furthermore, subtle discrimination can significantly affect the cognitive functioning of victims, leading to reduce performance (Walker et al., 2021)

For several decades, and particularly in recent history, philosophers such as (Bernasconi, 2012) psychologists such as (Kite & Whitley, 2016), and sociologists also including have actively engaged in the discussion on non-discrimination and equal rights regardless of race, religion, and belief. Their goal is to either describe the reality of discrimination or advocate for the ideal of equal and fair treatment for all. This study examines schemas from the perspective of individual behavioral perspectives and belief systems to identify a potential link between discrimination and prejudice. The belief system is defined by Usó-Doménech & Nescolarde-Selva (2016) as an interconnected structure of norms with an impact on one another.

By examining the ethnic minorities' schemas, our study delves into the shared patterns among them, aiming to identify the underlying factors that contribute to these patterns. According to data from (Statistics Finland, 2021), there has a total of 423,494 individuals who do not have Finnish Origin. Among this population, approximately 200,000 individuals are either currently employed or within the working age range. Foreigners represent one of the most vulnerable groups when it comes to experiencing discrimination and prejudice in the workplace (Jasinskaja-Lahti et al., 2007; Noreen, 2023; Nshom et al., 2022). The report on discrimination against ethnic groups reports enormous at <http://schalor.google.com>. Therefore, common patterns need to be identified for planning better interventions by authorities and psychologists. Studying their experiences, particularly in relation to their working lives, can lead to progress and improvements that enhance their ability to integrate into society, resulting in a happier and more fulfilling life.

In recent years, data collection has become easier, analysis has become cheaper, and various algorithms have emerged to uncover hidden information through analysis. Therefore, data mining techniques have significantly

advanced the field of digital humanities by enabling researchers to explore large volumes of data and extract meaningful insights for example, Fiil-Flynn et al., (2022). These techniques, combined with machine learning models, can identify relationships and patterns that may otherwise be obscured or challenging to discern (Jiang et al., 2020). By applying data mining to the study of schemas, we can better understand the underlying mechanisms that contribute to discriminatory behavior and subsequently develop targeted interventions to promote a more inclusive and diverse society.

Our research integrates both qualitative and quantitative data collection methods, including survey questionnaires and semi-structured interviews, to provide a comprehensive understanding of the experiences and perceptions of individuals who have encountered covert discrimination in their workplaces. Furthermore, by employing advanced statistical methods and machine learning models, we classify participants based on their schema profiles and demographic factors, revealing distinct schema profiles that may influence discriminatory behavior.

This study contributes to the digital humanities and data mining by demonstrating the potential of schema-guided data-driven analysis to decode subtle discrimination. By identifying and understanding the unique characteristics of different schema profiles, we can develop tailored interventions to address specific attitudes and behaviors associated with each profile, ultimately fostering a more inclusive and diverse society. Furthermore, our approach enables the creation of more specific and effective individualized interventions, providing valuable insights into the design of strategies and policies to combat discrimination at both the individual and societal levels.

This study aims to identify the underlying emotions and feelings experienced by individuals who have faced discrimination. Direct questions and self-reporting measurements have certain limitations, such as the potential for inaccurate responses, overreporting of discrimination, or fear of negative consequences. These issues can affect the reliability and validity of the data collected through these methods.

Related Researchers

Data Mining and Data Analysis

The rapid advancement of computational technology, including computers, mobile devices, and the internet has significantly enhanced data accessibility. Hence, these advancement results in the significance of data mining. Data mining refers to the process of analyzing the data in order to reach meaningful patterns that lead to constructing knowledge (Shruti et al., 2022). Data mining consists of several tasks such as data preprocessing, data transformation, pattern discovery, and result evaluation. Data mining and computational techniques have already been applied in various sectors of society to promote lifestyle and perform tasks faster in an efficient and effective manner.

In order to deepen our comprehension of society, data mining has been employed across diverse data sources, encompassing texts, images, audio, video, and social media. Its primary objective is to discern meaningful patterns and relationships that contribute to an enhanced understanding of societal dynamics. With the advancements in artificial intelligence (AI) technology, researchers have increasingly turned to data mining and AI techniques to address pressing issues such as discrimination, as exemplified by the work of Heinrichs (2022). Discrimination stands as one of the prominent challenges faced by contemporary society (Zhang et al., 2022), and leveraging data mining and AI can provide valuable insights and solutions to tackle this complex problem.

Discrimination and subtle discrimination

Therefore, in this study, the term “discrimination” refers to the systematic, intentional, and planned mistreatment of employees by their colleagues or superiors. According to the Merriam-Webster dictionary (Merriam Webster, 2015), discrimination means differentiating unfairly individuals or groups based on their characteristics, such as race, gender, or religion. Discrimination involves favoring one group over another without a legitimate reason. This can result in unfair treatment and unequal opportunities. Van Laer & Janssens (2011) identified three key

elements of subtle discrimination in the workplace. The first element of subtle discrimination, as noted by Van Laer & Janssens (2011), is that it is often unclear and can involve disempowerment disguised as empowerment. The second type of discrimination is based on power dynamics, including normalization, the legitimization of oneself, and the legitimization of others. entails disempowerment by making it seem as though they are empowering. The third type of discrimination is influenced by social discourses that are present in both workplace interactions and broader societal structures. These discourses can perpetuate discrimination and reproduce unequal treatment of individuals or groups based on their characteristics.

Sadly, in today's society, discrimination and prejudice have become widespread and pervasive. Minorities, in almost all societies, are particularly affected by discrimination and prejudice. This trend is also evident in Western countries, where there has been a recent surge in immigration. Simultaneously, the prevalence and visibility of hate speech have increased, particularly through social media platforms (Mossie & Wang, 2020). In Finland, Liebkind et al. (2016) showed that majority group members have a higher chance than minorities. Discrimination, however, can affect people of all nationalities, races, religions, and education levels. Rhead et al. (2021) demonstrated how harassment and discrimination have increased in the UK's National Health Service (NHS), particularly in the past five years. Kline et al. (2021) also found evidence supporting this issue, demonstrating that employees with distinctively black names make up less than 2% of the workforce compared to employees with distinctly white names. Likewise, Liebkind et al. (2016) reported that ethnic and gender discrimination during the recruitment process is prevalent in Finland. Their findings suggest that the majority group is more likely to be preferred in hiring over minority groups. Additionally, male applicants from the majority group experienced more discrimination than women did.

A shared understanding of the concept and the scope of discrimination is lacking, as it has been examined and defined by different academic fields. Coombs & King (2005) provided evidence for the identification of four distinct types of workplace discrimination: career advancement discrimination, punitive behavior discrimination, practice barriers discrimination, and hiring barriers discrimination. Discrimination is often associated with terms like bullying, and harassment. Rhead et al. (2021) pointed out that the term "bullying" is the most frequently used term and refers to offensive, insulting, or malicious behaviors in the workplace that can lead to physical and mental health problems. Likewise, according to the UK Public Equality Act 2010 (*Equality Act 2010*, 2010), harassment is another term that is used to describe unwanted conduct related to a protected characteristic that creates a degrading or offensive environment for the targeted individual. Rhead et al. (2021) distinguished discrimination from bullying and harassment. This definition states that discrimination occurs when an individual is treated unjustly due to their race, ethnicity, or possession of any of the protected characteristics, such as age, gender, disability, religion, sexual orientation, or race. Schulz et al. (2006) showed that discrimination has harmful effects on both the psychological and physical well-being of individuals, regardless of whether it is defined as bullying, harassment, or discrimination according to the various definitions provided in the literature.

Exploring Methods for Measuring Discrimination

Discrimination often occurs at the individual level, where people may face discrimination directly or actively discriminate against others. While individual self-reporting can be useful, it does not fully capture the underlying thought patterns, emotions, and experiences of both victims and discriminators.

Discrimination has been present in communities throughout history, and efforts to understand and address it have been ongoing. Social psychologists have developed theoretical frameworks to explain discrimination, including the social identity perspective, the Behaviors from Intergroup Affect and Stereotypes map, and the conceptualization of racism as an aversive phenomenon, as elaborated by Ramiah et al., (1996). Aversive racism represents the most extreme form of discrimination. Aversive racism, as a theory proposed by (Gaertner & Dovidio, 1986), refers to the extreme form of discrimination where people simultaneously maintain a belief in equality and prejudice. Generally, individuals are less likely to discriminate in situations where right and wrong are clearly defined, as discriminatory behaviors would be apparent to both oneself and others. However, aversive racists may

exhibit systematic discriminatory behaviors in situations where appropriate behaviors are not clearly defined or where they can rationally justify their actions based on factors other than race.

Researchers often applied mix-methods to analyze discrimination, for example, (van Daalen et al., 2022) collected data and applied random-effects meta-analyses and Cochran X^2 test and I^2 statistic. Similarly, Maxie-Moreman & Tynes (2022) applied standardized kurtosis and skewness values to assess the distribution of the data on their dataset. Furthermore, Maxie-Moreman & Tynes (2022) used IBM SPSS to compute the descriptive statistics. Despite conducting a thorough literature review, our investigation did not yield any studies that utilized machine learning algorithms for analysis and predicting trends related to discrimination or in the analysis of schema questionnaires.

Impact of Emotions and Feelings on Discrimination

Emotions and feelings are often used interchangeably, but they are distinct despite being interdependent. Emotions refer to the physiological states that arise from our subconscious, and they are often considered uncontrollable responses of our bodies when we are confronted with an event. In contrast, feelings are the conscious experiences that arise when we become aware of our emotions. While emotions may be automatic, feelings are subject to conscious interpretation and cognitive processing. Loewenstein et al., (2001) have shown that feelings have a significant impact on our decision-making, especially in situations of uncertainty, indicating that feelings and emotions can directly influence our behavior. In order to regulate our emotions, we engage in a variety of actions and behaviors, such as consuming hedonistic products, as demonstrated by Kemp & Kopp, (2011).

Individuals who have been subjected to discrimination commonly experience a diverse array of negative emotions, including but not limited to anger (Matheson & Anisman, 2009), frustration (Sutin et al., 2016), and sadness (Gill & Matheson, 2006), all of which can have detrimental effects on their psychological well-being. Additionally, discrimination is often linked to feelings of shame and self-doubt, which can have a profound impact on one's self-concept and level of confidence.

Feelings are generated by conscious cognitive processes, whereas emotions are automatic physiological responses to stimuli. Different methods can be employed to measure emotions, including subjective (self-report) (Jahedi & Méndez, 2014), behavioral (observable actions), and physiological (bodily changes) (Novitski et al., 2004) approaches (Scherer, 2005). To measure subjective behavior, researchers commonly use instruments such as questionnaires, rating scales, and experimental sampling. The Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (Peacock & Wong, 1990) is an example of a system used by scholars to measure subjective behavior.

Schemas Questionnaire

Humans interpret the world according to categorical rules. Schemas determine where new information fits into these rules. Our environment can be interpreted and predicted by using these schemas. According to psychology, schemas refer to patterns of behavior and thought that represent categories of information and their relationship. Aligned with this, (Merriam-Webster dictionary, 2021) defined it as a codification of experience such that they manifest in an organized way of perceiving and reacting to complex situations and stimuli in a particular organized way. (Arbib, 1992.) defines schemas as a common vocabulary among brain theorists, cognitive scientists, connectionists, ethologists, and kinesiologists, regardless of how they are enacted across industries. The schema theory was developed for people with chronic psychological problems who have difficulty making gains in cognitive therapy (Hawke & Provencher, 2011). Young et al., (2003a) identify early maladaptive schemas (EMS) as significant, pervasive characteristics developed at the root of childhood trauma. In general, Young et al., (2003) identified 18 EMS, which have been organized into five categories known as schema domains, which group EMS that tend to cooperate. Table 1 presents the 18 early maladaptive schemas (EMSs) with 5 schema domains of the Young Schema Questionnaire, third edition (YSQ-3).

Table 1 presents the 18 early maladaptive schemas (EMSs) with 5 schema domains of the YSQ-3.

Schema Domain	EMS	Description
Disconnection and rejection	1. Abandonment (AB) 2. Mistrust/Abuse (MA) 3. Emotional depredation (ED) 4. Defectiveness /Shame (DS) 5. Social Isolation /Alienation (SI)	The belief that a significant other will leave I am afraid that others will take advantage or lie. Lack of adequate emotional support The belief that they are flawed or worthless A feeling of separation from others
Impaired autonomy and performance	6. Dependence or incompetence 7. Vulnerability to harm or illness 8. Enmeshment/Undeveloped Self 9. Failure (FA)	A feeling of not being able to take care of oneself A belief that a catastrophe is imminent Individual identity is merged with another's Comparing oneself with others and feeling inadequate
Impaired limits	10. Entitlement or grandiosity (ET) 11. Insufficient self-control and self-discipline	A sense of superiority and of being more deserving than others. Having no control over one's emotions and impulses
Other Directedness	12. Subjugation 13. Self-Sacrifice 14. Approval-Seeking or Recognition-Seeking	One's own needs are not as important as those of others. Putting the needs of others ahead of one's own An increased desire for approval and recognition from others
Over vigilance and inhibition	15. Negativity/Pessimism 16. Emotional Inhibition 17. Unrelenting Standards and Hyper-Criticalness 18. Punitiveness	The tendency to focus on the negative aspects of life Expression of emotion is restricted. Having the drive to achieve perfection The belief that mistakes deserve punishment

Research Questions and Method

In this study, our objective is to utilize the data mining process to enhance the analysis of a tailored customized schema questionnaire, enabling a comprehensive examination of patterns and discernment of subtle discriminations. To achieve this, we address the following questions:

Research Questions

1. How do data mining and machine learning techniques facilitate the analysis of schemas questionnaire?
2. What schemas contribute to individuals' vulnerability to discrimination and engaging in discriminatory behavior?

Applied Methodology

In this mixed methods study, we utilized a combination of questionnaires and semi-structured interviews to collect both quantitative and qualitative data. The customized schema questionnaire was designed and prepared by the schema therapist leading this research. During the semi-structured interviews, participants were asked about their experiences of subtle discrimination in the workplace and their ability to recall specific negative incidents. We employed the Cross-Industry Standard Process for Data Mining (CRISP-DM), developed by Wirth & Hipp (2000), to analyze the data obtained from the questionnaire. The CRISP-DM process involves four stages, namely business understanding, data understanding, data preparation and modeling, and evaluation,

We employed the Cross-Industry Standard Process for Data Mining (CRISP-DM), developed by Wirth and Hipp (2000) to analyze the data obtained from the questionnaire. The CRISP-DM process involves four stages, namely business understanding, data understanding, data preparation and modeling, and evaluation, as shown in Figure 1, which illustrates the process of analyzing data and recognizing patterns.

Figure 1. The process of the analysis of the data

Data Collections: Questionnaire

To measure individuals' self- and job satisfaction, we administer custom-designed schema questionnaires. The survey comprises nine questions relating to demographics and 27 questions concerning their emotional state at the time of the assessment. In our classification, the questions are grouped into four factors, namely social isolation, failure, entitlement, and emotional state. Nonetheless, this report will only concentrate on the emotional state of the participants. We asked questions such as “*Most often, it has been difficult to find someone who listens to me, understands me, or takes into consideration my true needs and feelings.*” or “*The people around me have usually not been warm, holding me, or showing me affection*”. Figure 2 displays a sample of the Likert scale questions.

11. I feel alienated from other people. *
1. Completely untrue of me
 2. Mostly untrue of me
 3. Slightly more true than untrue
 4. Moderately true of me
 5. Mostly true of me
 6. Describes me perfectly

Figure 2: A sample of the survey questions

The questionnaire was shared through several social media channels, such as WhatsApp groups, LinkedIn groups, and Facebook groups, resulting in the collection of 91 samples from individuals of different nationalities residing in Finland. Among these participants, two were Finnish, while the birthplace of two others was not specified. However, all four individuals were excluded from the analysis.

Data Collections: Semi-Structured Interview

In addition to the questionnaire, we conducted concise semi-structured interviews with foreign workers who had been living in Finland for a long period. The selection of participants primarily based focused on their firsthand experience working for Finnish companies. Participants for the study were recruited through multiple channels, including universities, coffee shops, and word-of-mouth referrals from previous study participants. To maintain confidentiality, we assured participants that their identities would be kept anonymous throughout the research process and the reporting. Additionally, participants provided their consent to share their experiences as part of the study. During the interview, participants were commonly asked about various aspects related to their educational background, employment history, and the length of their stay in Finland. Additionally, participants were asked about their encounters with subtle discrimination, if any, and how they effectively dealt with such situations. This line of questioning aimed to gain insights into participants' personal experiences and their strategies for addressing any discriminatory encounters they may have faced.

The interviews were conducted by the first author on multiple occasions, with a preferred location being a coffee shop in Espoo, Finland. During the interviews, the interviewer actively took notes, which served as a valuable material for subsequent analysis and interpretation of the data. This note-taking process ensured that important details and key points from the interviews were captured accurately for further examination.

Data analysis methods

In this study, we have applied multivariate data analysis to distinguish the source of discriminatory behavior and differences between the groups and find the emotions or schemas that are responsible for the separation of the groups. The SIMCA software, version 17.02, was used to obtain all results reported in this study, with default procedures for data pre-treatment. MOCA is a multivariate statistical method that is used to analyze multiple sets of variables (blocks) simultaneously. The goal of MOCA is to identify the relationships between the variables within each block and between the different blocks. MOCA is particularly useful when there are complex relationships between variables in the dataset and it is widely used in many social science research datasets. Additionally, with the help of MOCA, we are able to identify the underlying common factors within each block and their relationship. Furthermore, MOCA is an unsupervised learning technique that identifies patterns and structures in the data without the need for a predefined outcome, in contrast to traditional statistical methods.

Results

Table 2 provides an overview of the study participants. Within our questionnaire, out of a total of 91 participants, 47 were identified as male, 43 as female, and 1 participant indicated their gender as binary. Likewise, during the interview phase, there were a total of 10 participants, with 7 identified as male and 3 as female.

Table 2 presents the profiles of the study participants.

Methods	Male	Female	Not binary
Questionnaire	47	43	1
Semi-structured Interview	7	3	0

Data Analysis: Questionnaire

The study involved 91 participants, and it was discovered that women had a slightly higher employment rate (40%) than men (39%), despite the fact that there were more male participants than female ones. Among the undergraduate participants (51%), roughly 24% were from Asia, 11% were from Europe, 7% were from Africa, 3% were from Eurasia, 3% were from North America, 1% were from South America, and 1% did not specify their country of birth on the questionnaire.

Figure 2 displays the regions represented by our participants, with the largest number from Asia ($n = 42$). Europe comes in second with 24 participants, followed by Africa, North America, and South America with 5, 5, and 3 participants, respectively.

Figure 2. The distribution of the participants based on geographical perspective

The qualifications of our participants are shown in Figure 3. The majority of participants have completed either a bachelor's degree ($n = 45$) or a master's degree ($n = 34$), while two hold a PhD, and a small number possess only a high school diploma ($n = 8$).

Figure 3. The qualifications of the participants

Our classification of participants' employment status is presented in Figure 4, including full-time, part-time, entrepreneurs, business owners, and self-employed. Students who registered as interns were considered unemployed, while postdocs were classified as full-time employees.

Figure 4. The employment status of the participant

Our analysis revealed that 72 (80%) participants were employed and earning an income, while 18 (20%) experienced difficulties in finding a job. For a detailed breakdown of the questionnaire data, see Appendix (A).

Figure 5 presents the multivariate analysis(Everitt & Dunn, 2013)) of the collected data. The analysis of the data gathered in this study, utilizing cluster analysis techniques and schema-based categorization, provides insight into the distribution patterns of the participants. The graph shows that most participants' responses cluster around the central region of the plot, indicating a strong consensus of opinions and attitudes among the respondents.

Figure 5. The cluster analysis of the participant's responses to the schema questions. The score plot (a) shows the distributions, patterns, and clusters of participants, and the loading plot (b) shows the pattern of the responses among the participants.

Figure 5 consists of two plots, a score plot (a) and a loading plot (b), which together provide insight into the patterns of responses among the participants. The $t_j [1]$ and $t_j [2]$, in the score, and similarly, $P_j [1]$ and $P_j [2]$, in loading plots, represent the first and second principal components. (Schema shortening: Emotional deprivation, ED; Abandonment, AB; Mistrust/Abuse, MA; Social isolation, SI; Failure, FA; Defective/Shame, DS; Entitlement, ET). The score plot (a) shows the distribution of participants based on their responses to the survey questions. Each individual is identified by a unique ID number and the size of their circle indicates the variance of their responses. Participants with similar answers are located close to each other, and those colored blue on the plot tend to have lower Likert scores than that colored red. The loading plot displays the patterns of the most important variables in the dataset, with each variable labeled according to the Likert scale of the participants' responses (0-5). Variables closer to the center of the plot have less impact on the variation, while those further away have a greater impact. For instance, in Figure 5(a), the red dots indicate individuals with more impact than the blue dots, and 5(b) shows that emotions have more impact on variance. The points in the circle far from the center represent different schemas, labeled as either Low (lower than average score) or High (higher than average score) for each schema. Overall, the loading plot shows that the schemas have a greater impact on the variation than the individual questions, suggesting that computing schemas are an effective way of understanding the variance. The high-scored schemas are positively associated with participants located on the right side of the score plot (red), while the low-scored schemas are associated with participants on the left side (blue). Table 3 provides additional and supportive information on the mean values and standard deviations of the schemas.

Table 3. The standard deviation and mean values of low- and high-scored categories. H and L in the first column stand for higher and lower-than-average scores for each schema, while SD shows the standard deviation and N numbers for each group.

Schema	N	Mean (H)	SD	Mean (L)	SD
ED	91	0.263736	0.443099	0.736264	0.443099
AB	91	0.241758	0.430521	0.241758	0.430521
MA	91	0.296703	0.459335	0.703297	0.459335

<i>DS</i>	<i>91</i>	<i>0.373626</i>	<i>0.486446</i>	<i>0.626374</i>	<i>0.486446</i>
<i>SI</i>	<i>91</i>	<i>0.131868</i>	<i>0.340222</i>	<i>0.868132</i>	<i>0.340222</i>
<i>FA</i>	<i>91</i>	<i>0.120879</i>	<i>0.327793</i>	<i>0.879121</i>	<i>0.327793</i>
<i>ET</i>	<i>91</i>	<i>0.384615</i>	<i>0.4892</i>	<i>0.615385</i>	<i>0.4892</i>

The standard deviation of the schemas indicates that the spread of the data between H and L is equally distributed. In all the schema failure (FA) with (0.327793) has the smallest standard deviation. This indicated that FA has the least amount of variability or dispersion from the mean. Furthermore, social isolation (SI) comes as the next least SD (0.34222) in our data set. In contrast, defectiveness/shame (DS) has the highest standard deviation. This implies that with a wider spread of data points, participants have less consensus on this schema.

In order to conduct a more detailed analysis and gain a comprehensive understanding of the schemas, we utilized a multivariate analysis, as shown in Table 4. The first group of components listed are the joint components. They summarize the systematic information that is found in at least two blocks of variables at the same time, i.e., information in the contributing blocks that is common, or joint, between them. Those blocks that are not contributing to a listed joint component will have no value for that component. The first and second joint components in Table 4 are joint between emotion and question and contain information from emotion, while the third joint component contains information from demographic data. The second group of components is the block's unique components. They express the systematic information that is unique to a given block, i.e., information in the block that is unrelated to all the other blocks. Being unique, these components are only relevant for one block at a time and should therefore only be looked at column-wise (within blocks) and never row-wise (across blocks). One unique component from the question and three unique components from emotions are shown in Table 4. The R2X - is the fraction of block variation modeled in the component, and the R2X (cum) - is the cumulative R2X for the block up to the specified component.

Table 4. Overview of three blocks: component analysis, question, emotion, and demographic. The two columns for each block of the MOCA components are R2X, - the fraction of block variation modeled in the component, and R2X(cum) - the cumulative R2X for the block up to the specified component.

Component	R2X	R2X(cum)	R2X	R2X(cum)	R2X	R2X(cum)
Model		0,215		0,846		0,111
Blocks	Question		Emotion		Demographics	
Joint components		0,128		0,614		0,111
1	0,072	0,072	0,434	0,434	--	--
2	0,0289	0,101	0,179	0,614	--	--
3	0,0275	0,128	--	--	0,111	0,111

Unique components		0,087		0,232		0
1	0,087	0,087	0,0846	0,0846	--	--
2	--	--	0,0755	0,16	--	--
3	--	--	0,0718	0,232	--	--

Table 4 shows that emotions appear to have the highest (84.6%) explanatory power, while the demographics (11%) have the least contribution. Hence, emotions play a crucial role in the explanation of the variation observed in the data. Consistent with the findings in Table 3, this analysis further confirms that there are no strong correlations observed between variables belonging to different blocks, i.e., no direct correlation exists between emotions and demographics.

Figure 6 presents a visual representation of the origin or source of variance as depicted in Table 4. In Figure 6 (b), the primary source of variance (PC1 direction) is characterized by high levels of MA (mistrust/abuse) and AB (abandonment), followed by ED (emotional deprivation), SI (social isolation), and DS (Defectiveness/Shame), with lower levels of FA (failure) and ET (entitlement). This suggests that the mentioned schemas are the most influential factors in the schema profiles within the first principal component. Aligning with this, the secondary source of variance (PC2 direction, Figure 6 (c) shows the highest effect from the schema ET, low effects from FA, ED, and DS, and no effects from MA, AB, and SI. This indicates that the second principal component captures the variance primarily driven by ET, with minor contributions from FA, ED, and DS, and no influence from MA, AB, or SI. The third source of variance comes from the demographic variables, number of employees in the organization, gender, employment status, education, geographical origin, and finally work experience, respectively; the percentage of foreign employees shows the least correlation, Figure 6(d).

Additionally, the unique features observed in the R2 overview might represent a specific pattern of data with a distinct schema profile that is not captured by the joint components (blue colored in Figure 6). Even though each unique component explains around 8% of variance (Table 4) they may reveal specific behavior of individuals that is not covered by joint components. It covers the ambivalent behavior that may not be predictable, that will not be covered in this article.

Summary of variance from data blocks

(a)

(b) First joint principal component

(c) Second joint principal component

(d) Third joint principal component

Figure 6. MOCA model R2 overview represents (a) a summary of variance from data blocks, and three joint components shown by the MOCA R2 overview (b, c, d) along with the variable pattern of variance for each component(e).

The MOCA model provides an insightful framework to understand multivariate data structures by decomposing the total variance in the data into the variations related to individual data blocks and the common variance shared between the blocks. This allows for a comprehensive exploration of the associations and interconnections within and between the blocks of variables. R2 overview of the MOCA analysis shown in (Figure 6) reveals the primary (b), secondary(c), and tertiary (d) sources of variance of the data. The plots highlight that the largest effect comes from questions and emotions, respectively the first component (7.2% 43.4% and the second component (2.9% 17.9%). The third component that captures the least variance has its origin from the demographic's variable (2.8% 11.1%) from question and demographics respectively.

The R2 overview in the MOCA model represents the explained variance of each component in each block. This helps to understand the relative importance of different components in explaining the variance of each block. A higher R2 value for a component indicates that the component is more important in explaining the variance in the respective block. The first joint component (b), is characterized by high MA (Mistrust/Abuse) & AB (Abandonment), followed by ED (Emotional Deprivation), SI (Social Isolation) & DS (Defectiveness/Shame), and ending with lower levels of FA (Failure) & ET (Entitlement). The secondary joint component (c), is characterized by schema ET that

has the highest effect, FA, ED, and DS have a low effect, and MA, AB, and SI show no effect. And finally, the third joint component (d) explains the variance originated by demographics.

Figure 7 shows the loading plot of the third principal component as a column plot of demographic variables. The variables above the zero line are positively correlated to the principal component and those below the line are negatively correlated to the principal component.

Figure 7. Column plot of demographic variables.

Figure 8. The positive and negative loading plots of the schema profiles and demographic variables.

Figure 8 illustrates the association between schemas and demographics. The schemas are represented by both negative and positive plots, indicating their magnitude and direction. For instance, when comparing components 2 and 3, it can be observed that in Africa and Europe, males, as well as unemployed undergraduates, exhibit high levels of entitlement and emotion deprivation. However, in Asia, females,

employed individuals, and graduates demonstrate lower levels of entitlement and emotional deprivation. The key finding is that FA and shame MA are negatively correlated with positive and negative demographics.

Summary of Data Analysis (Questionnaire)

The first component (PC1) captures most of the variance and is characterized by high levels of certain emotional schemas such as Mistrust/Abuse (MA), Abandonment (AB), Emotional Deprivation (ED), Social Isolation (SI), and Defectiveness/Shame (DS), whereas it has lower associations with Failure (FA) and Entitlement (ET). This suggests that individuals with high values on PC1 are more likely to experience these intense emotional schemas. On the other hand, lower values on PC1 are associated with lesser experiences of FA and ET. These findings suggest a complex interplay between different emotional schemas in the experience of subtle discrimination, which may require targeted interventions tailored to the specific emotional profile of the individual.

The second component (PC2) mainly captures the variance associated with the Entitlement (ET) schema, along with minor contributions from Failure (FA), Emotional Deprivation (ED), and Defectiveness/Shame (DS). This suggests that individuals with high values on PC2 may have a stronger sense of entitlement, coupled with minor feelings of failure, emotional deprivation, and shame. Conversely, low values on PC2 are associated with less pronounced feelings of entitlement, and slightly increased feelings of mistrust/abuse, abandonment, and social isolation.

The third component (PC3) captures the demographic variances in the data, with certain demographic characteristics being positively associated and others negatively associated. The positive associations with PC3 include continents (Europe and Africa), gender (Male and NB), unemployment, work experiences [(0-3), (6-10), and >15 years], number of employees in the organization more than 20, and percentage of foreign employees [(1-5) % and (15-30) %]. On the other hand, negative associations with PC3 include continents (Asia, Eurasia, and America), gender (Female), specific types of employment, work experiences [(3-6), and (10-15) years], number of employees in the organization [(1-5), and (6-20)], and percentage of foreign employees >30%. These findings suggest that certain demographic characteristics are more likely to be associated with the experience of subtle discrimination than others, which underscores the importance of considering these factors in the design and implementation of interventions to promote equity and inclusivity.

Hence, the model suggests that the "emotion" and "demographics" blocks are significant in explaining the variance in the data, with no globally joint component contributing to the variance. This might indicate that the factors within each block "emotion" and "demographics" operate independently in their influence on the data. Further research might be needed to explore the interactions between these blocks and understand the implications of these findings.

Data Analysis: Semi-structured Interview

Our selection process for interviewees involved careful consideration of individuals who had encountered instances of discrimination. However, despite our rigorous efforts, the task of finding interviewees who engaged in discriminatory practices proved arduous, if not unfeasible. Consequently, all participants included in our study exclusively shared personal narratives of experiencing discrimination.

The interviewers commonly introduced the subjects with a brief overview of their age and length of residency in Finland. By utilizing the semi-structured format, the participants were afforded the freedom to share their experiences, which were often accompanied by sentiments of anger and rage. Notably, it was evident that all the

participants articulated their anger in a manner that suggested recent encounters with subtle discrimination. The quotes presented below are excerpts from the interview transcript. *“I was discriminated against 15 years ago. My efforts to get help from legal and government officials were fruitless. This left me with no choice but to thread the discriminator. In the end, it was a good decision because the problem was permanently solved. Yah (office emp.), 54, 30 years in Finland”*.

Table 5 illustrates the user profiles of the participants involved in the semi-structured interviews. It is important to note that the names listed in the table are pseudonyms, employed to ensure confidentiality and anonymity, and do not correspond to the actual identities of the sampled individuals.

Table 5: User profile of the selected candidate for the interview

Users	Age	Gender	Education	Employment	No YRS in Finland
U1 (Far)	60	Male	MSc.	Self Emp.	31
U2 (Dav)	54	Male	High School Dip.	Office Emp.	30
U3 (Mga)	59	Male	Ph.D.	Emp.	30
U4 (Rez)	51	Male	BSc.	Emp.	30
U5 (Hei)	24	Female	High School Dip	Un Emp.	Native
U6(Mos)	50	Male	MSc.	Un Emp	25
U7 (Kai)	43	Female	MSc.	Emp.	Native
U8 (Jab)	55	Male	High School Dip	Emp.	11
U9 (Jay)	58	Male	High School Dip	Self Emp.	31
U10(Fer)	54	Female	MSc.	Un Emp.	31

Among the total participants (n = 10), three were female (n = 3), while the remaining were male. The majority of the participants demonstrated higher levels of educational attainment, with one holding a BSc, four holding MSc degrees, one holding a Ph.D. degree, and the remainder having completed high school diplomas. At the time of the interview, the majority of our participants were either employed or self-employed (n = 8), while only two participants (n = 2) were unemployed. Additionally, two of the participants were natives, while the remaining individuals had foreign origins.

Discussions

We have applied various statistical and clustering analyses to verify the pattern of schemas among the foreign workforce in this study. Our findings demonstrate that employing data-driven analysis offers an opportunity to examine diverse and nonlinear psychosocial data. Furthermore, it provides valuable insight into the underlying variations that define the intricate nature of polysemous schema problems. A better understanding of schema-based complexities in human behavior and accurate subgrouping of the population has the potential to enhance risk assessment, develop data-driven models for well-being, and provide effective solutions for social problems. We have utilized data mining MOCA and multivariate analysis to gain a comprehensive understanding of the received schema-based questionnaire data. By employing this approach, we examine the data from different perspectives, including individual and group views, allowing for a thorough analysis. The complexity of the data sets, variables, and associated information necessitates the use of new approaches to uncover relationships between the datasets. The objective of conducting this study was to identify common schemas that could help determine whether an individual is experiencing subtle discrimination.

Subtle discrimination against individuals, organizations, and society as a whole can pose both physical and psychological challenges. Discrimination and prejudice are commonplace in modern society, with prejudice referring to a negative attitude towards a victim, while discrimination involves hostile behavior directed at the victim. Subtle discrimination is characterized as the covert unfair treatment of a specific individual. According to (Jones et al., 2017), subtle discrimination can vary in terms of its degree of subtlety, formality, and intentionality.

The authors conceptualize subtlety as a negative or ambiguous behavior towards a social minority group due to their membership in that group. This behavior may not always be conscious and may imply ambiguous intent. Hence, discrimination subtly depends on the extent to which it occurs. (Jones et al., 2017) distinguish between formal and interpersonal discrimination as two different spectra of discrimination. Interpersonal discrimination can take many forms, including rudeness, harassment, and general hostility toward minorities. On the other hand, formal discrimination is job-related and subject to rules, regulations, and laws that either prevent it from occurring or respond appropriately when it does, such as a decision not to hire or promote an employee based on discriminatory grounds.

The present study aims to explore the impact of subtle discrimination on a victim's psychological and physiological well-being by addressing the research questions. This study aims to identify the feelings that are associated with specific schemas at the time of the study. Therefore, our objective was to explore the feelings experienced by foreign workforces in particular, rather than relying solely on traditional job satisfaction questionnaires. As far as the literature review indicates, this is the first time that a customized schema questionnaire has been employed to assess the schema patterns in group setups.

Our approach presents an initial step toward identifying subtle discrimination through a schema questionnaire. By utilizing a schema questionnaire, we aim to identify potential cognitive frameworks of schemas that contribute to discriminatory behaviors and biases. The identification of schemas not only assists therapists in providing more efficient support to victims but also facilitates individuals in overcoming discrimination at a faster pace. Our approach holds promise in addressing subtle forms of discrimination and promoting more effective interventions for supporting victims.

1. How do data mining and machine learning techniques facilitate the analysis of schemas questionnaire?

Traditional statistical approaches are commonly utilized in the analysis of social science datasets descriptive statistics such as measuring central tendencies, i.e., mean, median, and mode with measuring the dispersion of the data, e.g., standard deviation and range. Additionally, Inferential statistics help to draw conclusions about the population of sample data among the most known techniques, hypothesis testing, confidence intervals, and analysis of variances (ANOVA). Furthermore, Regression analysis helps to analyze the relationship between a dependent variable and independent variables. Factor analysis is yet another technique that is widely used to identify the underlying factors or dimensions within a dataset.

In the data mining approach especially the multivariate and multi-block data, a characteristic common in many social science research datasets, including ours. It can work with multiple groups of variables (blocks) simultaneously, considering the internal structure within each block and the relationships between blocks. This is particularly beneficial when the research involves multi-dimensional concepts, such as schemas and subtle discrimination, that cannot be effectively captured by a single variable or block. Furthermore, MOCA is an unsupervised learning technique that can identify underlying patterns and structures in the data without being guided by a pre-specified outcome. This is contrasted with traditional statistical methods, which typically require a pre-specified hypothesis to test. MOCA, therefore, can reveal novel insights that were not previously hypothesized, thereby advancing our understanding of the complex phenomenon under study. In contrast to statistical methods such as Fisher's test, also known as Fisher's exact test, is a statistical significance test used in the analysis of contingency tables. Although it is a powerful tool for assessing the independence of two categorical variables, its utility is limited when we need to analyze multi-dimensional, continuous, and complex relational data. In addition, Fisher's test does not provide information on the direction and magnitude of the relationships among variables. It merely tests the null hypothesis of no association between variables. In contrast, MOCA can provide detailed insights into the relationships among variables, including their relative importance, the direction of their effects, and the nature of their interactions.

By conducting a comprehensive dataset analysis using multivariate analysis and a machine learning algorithm, we were able to thoroughly examine our dataset. Our analysis encompassed studying individual schema questionnaire

data, as well as identifying a common pattern among all participants. Moreover, our application of a machine learning algorithm enabled us to make predictions regarding trends, although these findings are considered beyond the scope of this report.

2. *What schemas contribute to individuals' vulnerability to discrimination and engaging in discriminatory behavior?*

Widmayer (2004) defined schemas as categorized rules that humans use to give meaning to the ways they interact in the world. Based on the Widmayer (2004) definition, through schemas, we interpret and also predict the events occurring in or surrounding us. Based on this definition, we are able to apply the theory of schema to interpret and predict an individual's experience of discrimination. This study sought to examine the participants' experiences of discrimination through the schema questionnaire. The question categories enabled the participants to reconstruct their previous experiences, i.e., discrimination. Furthermore, as the schemas are considered individual facts, we applied data mining approaches that helped us identify individual participants with their associated schemas; for example, figure 5, reveals the clustering analysis of the participants' responses and their patterns within the groups. This type of analysis not only shows each participant's unique and dependent schema on the reconstructed experience but also their status among their peers. The customized schema questionnaire, as shown in Figure 6, helped us investigate and learn about the participants' constructed mental models. Schemas represent an individual's mental structures (Marshall, 1995) that are constructed over time by various social, personal, and cultural experiences. Hence, one may conclude that the result of this study is also indicative of our participants' perception and attitude toward the environment which they have constructed. It is self-evident that people's prior experiences and mental models, e.g., constructed even through childhood may influence (Harris & Curtin, 2002) their behavior and perception. This is applicable both for the discriminator and their victim. For example, having a negative mental model of specific ethnic or racial groups leads to unfair treatment of colleagues, or subordinates. Furthermore, schemas also help us recognize that we are being discriminated against.

The results from the MOCA analysis shown in Figure 6 summarize which schemas are important according to the data. The results have also been classified as the primary and secondary sources of variance. Two distinguishable schema profiles are classified. One of the profiles includes the schemas that might lead to being prone to discrimination. The other schema profile includes schemas that may lead to discrimination against others. In this study, we adopted a different approach to uncovering schemas that contribute to subtle discrimination. Identifying the emotions and cognitive frameworks associated with discrimination, particularly in its subtle forms, presents challenges due to the elusive nature of defining discrimination and its occurrence (Shen & Dhanani, 2015). However, we confidently offer our response to questions, supported by our thorough analysis, and proceed to justify it with existing literature. Hence, our answer provides insights into the psychological schemas necessary for understanding subtle discrimination while avoiding methodological argumentation, which is out of the scope of this paper.

The primary source of variance was characterized by high levels of mistrust/abuse (MA), abandonment (AB), emotional deprivation (ED), social isolation (SI), and defectiveness/shame (DS) Figures (5-b), (6-b), and (6-e). The prominence of these schemas suggests their importance in understanding subtle discrimination, aligning with previous literature, for example, the work of (Williamson et al., 2019) which explores the role of discrimination and medical mistrust. Their findings indicate that there is a correlation between previous discrimination experiences and medical mistrust. Furthermore, Williamson et al. identified that racial and ethnic background influence mistrust. The higher the level of mistrust, the more discrimination is experienced. This is visible in our study, among participants, as indicated in Figure (6-b) mistrust received the highest value. This indicates that our participants had this schema at the time of our investigation. This finding also aligns with research done by (Mikrut et al., 2022), which identified that discrimination involves mistrust and rejection schemas. During the semi-structured interview session, our participants also emphasized the prevailing mistrust. For example, *“I was discriminated against 15 years ago. My efforts to get help around, as well as legal and government officials, were fruitless. I decided to leave, In the end, it was a good decision because the problem was permanently solved. Yah (Office emp.), 54, 30 years in Finland”*.

Unlike Williamson et al., (2019), our results indicate that the participants' origins did not significantly depend on their emotions (responses to the discrimination) figure (6-d). This is because all our participants were of foreign origin except two, therefore, their votes were not statistically significant. The abandonment schema actually developed during the early childhood period, when the child was separated from the caregivers. Therefore, the brain gets alert at a very early age when it comes to our surroundings, caregivers, relationships, and traits that we receive from immediate partners or our bosses. Early maladaptive schemas, including abandonment schemas, impact the behavior of adolescents, as indicated by Khorramdel et al., (2013). We tend to try to hold on to the relationship, which is constructed. In our study, the abandonment schema also received a high score (Figure 5b, Figure 6b). This is rooted in the same fact that our participants put extensive effort into keeping the relationship intact in society, the workplace, or at home. Chew et al., (2020) disclosed that the victims of discrimination often suffer from abandonment. Our result shows that the abandonment schema has the highest scorers among our participants.

Lopes et al., (2021) show that age and loneliness are the two main factors contributing to the feeling of abandonment. Therefore, this fear specifically appears more in situations where the person is in conflict, e.g., when experiencing discrimination. Norman (1981) demonstrated that the schema was invoked by other schemas or by external stimulation. Furthermore, Bernstein et al., (2012) demonstrated that fear of abandonment is the result of attachment anxieties. Anxiety, guilt, and shame are also triggers for invoking this schema, as indicated in Carter and Forsyth (2010). Our analysis demonstrates that the abandonment schema was overwhelmingly invoked in our participants because of external triggers. The feelings of guilt and shame were also raised during the interview session because of abandonment, for example, *“Over 25 years, I worked as an expert for a government organization in Helsinki. I was degraded and required to perform tasks that went against my educational and professional background by our new director. He fired me three years ago. Every day has been a kickoff day since then, and I have received psychiatric help and been under medication. Ema, 50, 25 years in Finland.”*

Personality traits significantly influence emotional expression and behavior (Bono & Vey, 2007). Consequently, there exists a dynamic interplay between individual dispositions and the manifestation of emotions. Individuals with strong egos that are attached to a sense of shame, distrust, and abuse may be more susceptible to experiencing distress from seemingly minor, unfair treatment. Therefore, the extent of suffering experienced is contingent upon the intensity and severity of an individual's characteristics. Individuals lacking such schemas are less likely to exhibit similar behaviors, leading to more appropriate reactions when faced with discrimination. Conversely, individuals with pessimistic tendencies tend to perceive things negatively. The presence of shame, mistrust, and abusive schemas in such individuals can contribute to heightened emotional responses even in the face of minor triggers. In our analysis, we pursue to investigate what prevailing schemas that impact an individual subject to discrimination which is depicted in Figure (6-b). We assumed that these are the primary source of variance in our data. Based on the analyses the MA, AB, ED, and SI schemas received the highest scores. Figure 6 (b and e) indicates that individuals exhibiting elevated levels of MA, AB, ED, and SI schemas may be more susceptible to perceiving or experiencing discrimination. The amplification of these schemas might increase sensitivity to issues of trust, abandonment, emotional deprivation, and social isolation. This observation is congruent with the findings of Lepore & Brown (1997) who suggested that individuals with pronounced negative schemas, such as mistrust or abandonment, are more likely to interpret ambiguous actions as discriminatory. Conversely, the entitlement (ET) schema emerged as a significant factor in the secondary source of variance Figure (6-C). This finding is significant in shedding light on those who might engage in discriminatory behavior toward others. A pronounced ET schema, characterized by a strong sense of self-importance and superiority, may increase the likelihood of exhibiting discriminatory behavior. This aligns with the work of Tilly et al., (2001) which found a relationship between feelings of entitlement and the propensity to discriminate against others. Furthermore, Askari (2019) explores the schemas and beliefs that result in anger and aggression and identifies that mistrust/ abuse are the most schemas that impact anger. In our studies also mistrust and abandonment gain the highest score, is this because the conditions and the context trigger the high score (Figure 5-b and 6-b&e) on mistrust and abandonment? Or the majority of our participants suffer and carry the early childhood maladaptive schemas. The possibility of subtle discrimination for those who have higher scores for subjugation schemas, self-sacrifice schemas, and approval and

recognition schemas. Bernstein (2002) and May et al., (2022) showed that childhood emotional abuse and neglect are a form of emotional abuse that impacts adulthood through emotional triggers. In their childhood, often these groups are controlled by their parents and seek attention to get their parents' attention (Young et al., 2003) explored that narcissism is positively associated with entitlement schema while vulnerable narcissism is positively associated with subjugation schema. Additionally, Dion (2002) identified that increasing entitlement feelings lead to greater tolerance for inequality, which in turn leads to discrimination. In our study, entitlement did not receive a very high score (Figure 6-b). This recommends that those who fill out the questionnaire have not acted or behaved discriminatorily toward others. On the other hand, the subjugation and self-sacrifice receive a high score, which indicates that the participants were potential discrimination targets. The subjugation and self-sacrifice of people as shown by Pincus & Lukowitsky (2010) often have shame, anger, negative self-image, interpersonal sensitivity, and social withdrawal behavior, for example, *“I was discriminated against and sought help through various legal means to overcome, but I was not successful. Later, I realized that in Finland the law is only applied to native Finns and not to people of non-Finnish descent. Far, 60, 31 in Finland”*. Entitlement people used the subjugation people unfairly and they enjoy doing that since they get satisfied with the power that they enforced

Reliability and validity of the results

The aim of this study is to raise awareness about the impact of subtle discrimination by utilizing a schema questionnaire and conducting group comparisons. The main challenges in this study related to the small sample size that made analysis difficult especially applying PCA analysis. Since (Shaukat et al., 2016) have demonstrated that a sample size of 40 is adequate for obtaining stable PCA results, we were convinced to utilize PCS analysis in our study. Therefore, the results of this study are valid within the specific context of our conducted research. In order to gain a better understanding of patterns of emotional dysfunction we firmly believe that further research is necessary. This future research should encompass additional schemas and involve a larger sample size. Therefore, it is important to note that the findings of our study are only valid within the specific context and environment of our research. In order to draw a more comprehensive conclusion, it may be necessary to gather more systematic data and increase the sample size.

Furthermore, in this study, the analysis is focused mainly on those people that demonstrated negative emotions, and the comparison between different clusters such as low and medium satisfaction was not analyzed since we think this topic is out of the scope of this study and research questions. However, the analysis of emotions and demographic factors leading to varying levels of satisfaction will be presented in a separate publication.

Conclusions and Future Work

Our approach in this study is centered around identifying individual schemas within group setups. As such, our analysis serves as an initial step to encourage further exploration by researchers seeking alternative approaches to identify and address organizational issues. To validate our findings regarding schemas related to victims and discriminators, we compare them with existing literature in the field. By carefully examining and aligning our results with previous studies, our aim was to ensure the reliability and consistency of our findings. A mixed-method approach was employed to collect data from foreigners residing in the Helsinki metropolitan area. We collected data using the questionnaire to understand the overall schema and experience. Researchers collect semi-structured data directly from participants who have experienced subtle discrimination. Therefore, we believe that the data and analysis presented in this paper are reliable and support the arguments we have made.

The findings indicated that the primary sources of emotional impact on our users during the study were as follows: mistrust/abuse, abandonment, emotional deprivation, social isolation, and shame, along with lower levels of failure and entitlement. In contrast, demographic variables such as the number of employees in the organization, gender, employment status, education, participant origin, and even work experience show no correlation with our results.

Our study aimed to provide research-based evidence that will contribute to improving the overall well-being of minority ethnic workers by better targeted and more effective and advantageous management. Furthermore, the results of this study are the first step toward raising awareness and identifying and eradicating inhuman behavior in the workplace.

Our study does not consider discrimination to be racist even though it is often rooted in racism. The impacts of discrimination and prejudice on victims are different from those of unintentional racist behavior in the workplace. When we asked interviewees if they had been targeted for racism, their emotional expression was not as strong as when they spoke about their experiences with discrimination. Thus, discrimination in memory is always associated with strong emotions. The victim likely believes that the event is happening right now, and that passing time is not a healer for them. In conclusion, the results of this study suggest that the experience of subtle discrimination is a multifaceted phenomenon that is influenced by a complex interplay of emotional schemas and demographic factors. These findings can guide the development of interventions to address subtle discrimination by targeting the specific emotional schemas and demographic factors associated with the experience of discrimination.

As a part of our future plans, we aim to conduct additional studies with a broader audience. In these studies, we intend to utilize various data mining and machine learning algorithms to predict potential challenges and develop interventions that can provide assistance.

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